

AND PLACE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO WORK ACTIVITY OF UNIVERSITY TEACHERS

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Annotation. Educating the young generation, providing them with the education and upbringing process based on the requirements of the times, requires today's pedagogues not only to be experts in their fields, but also to acquire innovative and psychological knowledge at the same time. In the twenty-first century, which is the age of information, it is impossible to imagine the educational process without modern technology and psychological knowledge.

Keywords. Pedagogue, education, education, introvert, extrovert,

Introduction part. According to the report of the Statistics Agency at the beginning of the 2022/2023 academic year, the number of students studying in general education institutions in Uzbekistan was about 6.5 million. Undoubtedly, one of the most responsible jobs in society is the work of pedagogues working in the educational process. In our article, we try to highlight the importance and role of psychological knowledge in improving the effectiveness of the educational system.

The main part. The role of teachers is incomparable in the formation of the spiritual formation of the young generation and the formation of its system of views on the world. In general, the role of our pedagogues together with parents is significant and important in all life processes, their norms, a person's behavior in the way of life from the family to the street, finding a place in the society. Currently, the number of pedagogues working in general secondary schools in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 547,700 as of 2023-2024 (statistics agency). Of course, these are only pedagogues in the field of general secondary education, and besides, the number of pedagogues working in higher education and non-state educational organizations is quite significant. It goes without saying that the pedagogic field is one of the areas that should be studied and recognized in society.

The educational process will be more effective if the pedagogue works directly with the human personality, knowing what psychological changes occur in the student at different age periods and chooses the teaching method based on the age of the audience.

In particular, the junior school age is distinguished from other age periods by its several psychological characteristics. The period of junior school age in psychological literature covers the period from six to ten years. During this period,

the child is now experiencing the process of adaptation to learning activities, and the transition from play activities to direct learning activities can be quite difficult for the child. At the same time, rapid developments in cognitive processes are observed in the student at this time. He is first prepared psychologically for school education. Consequently, his psyche develops enough to acquire knowledge. A child of this age is distinguished from children of other ages by his sharpness of perception, clarity, purity, accuracy, his curiosity, kindness, benevolence, trustworthiness, brightness of his imagination, strength of his memory, clarity of thinking.

Of course, a teacher who does not know these features will inevitably face difficulties in working with students and effectively conducting the educational process. Similarly, each age period has its own characteristics, and conducting educational processes taking into account these characteristics at different stages of education requires a modern teacher not only to have deep knowledge of his specialty, but also to be aware of psychological knowledge. Above, we tried to shed some light on the period of elementary school age and its psychological characteristics and the importance of these characteristics in the educational process. On the other side of the story, pedagogical activity and how well one knows one's specialty is one of the important factors that determine the quality and effectiveness of education. A number of requirements and tasks are set for the pedagogue to effectively organize his activities.

1. Arming future teachers with the theoretical and methodological foundations of pedagogical skills.
2. Acquiring the system of knowledge about the components of the science of pedagogical skills, such as pedagogical technique, pedagogical cooperation (communication), pedagogical delicacy, pedagogical ability, educator's skill, management of the educational-educational process, speech culture, pedagogical creativity.
3. Future teachers will develop the need and desire to independently master the secrets of pedagogical skills reflected in our national customs and traditions and the rich creative heritage of Central Asian thinkers.
4. Based on the acquired pedagogical-psychological and methodical knowledge, skills and qualifications, each future teacher forms his personal pedagogical skills.
5. They regularly master the theoretical and practical foundations of organizing and managing the educational process based on the latest modern methods and forms typical of world standards.
6. To improve their professional skills, teachers acquire the forms, methods and tools of personal and creative professional development.

7. They form their professional skills based on the use of modern information technologies and the portal system.

The solution of these goals and tasks teaches the teacher-educator to keep up with the times, to live with the pain of educating young people and to see the future clearly. Each teacher will conscientiously imagine the actual problems, goals and tasks of our country and teach them to use their opportunities, knowledge, and experiences with enthusiasm, and educate them to have the skills of a creative approach to pedagogical activities.¹

In conclusion, we can say that in order to effectively organize pedagogical activities in the current educational process, it is necessary not only to be able to use the field of expertise, but also to be able to correctly use modern technologies, to know well the psychology of people receiving education, and to use them in their place. has become one of the leading factors determining the quality of education.

Used literature

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